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Model Caching, Training, and Compression

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Authors:	Victor Croisfelt (AAU), Beatriz Soret (AAU), Deniz Gunduz (ICL), Meng Hua (ICL), Fotios Stavrou (EUR), Marios Kountouris (EUR), Paolo Di Lorenzo (CNIT), Simone Scardapane (CNIT), Jary Pomponi (CNIT)
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Abstract

This deliverable investigates how future Sixth Generation (6G) wireless networks can efficiently manage Machine Learning (ML) models through coordinated (i) *caching*, (ii) *training*, and (iii) *compression* across the protocol stack, a key objective of the 6G-GOALS project in realizing Artificial Intelligence (AI)-native networks. The study spans five application frameworks, each targeting a specific subset of these model-management functions. **Contribution A** focuses on model caching and model compression within the Semantic Data Acquisition (SEMDAS) framework, where a shared embedding space and semantic relevance scoring govern when distributed Internet-of-Things (IoT) devices transmit data, turning random access into a context-aware, collision-sensitive process that reduces redundant traffic. **Contribution B** targets model caching for real-time multimodal inference in distributed Audio-Visual (AV) systems, proposing a neuro-inspired solution that maintains temporal coherence of multimodal received data under stochastic, modality-specific delays while leveraging cached multimodal foundation models at the edge. **Contribution C** addresses model training and model compression by introducing an efficient split-training methodology for transformer-based architectures, combining batch- and token-level compression to lower communication overhead in Split Learning (SL) without sacrificing accuracy. **Contribution D** advances model training and model compression through Reinforcement Learning methods for delayed and constrained systems, where decisions must balance performance and resource costs under non-negligible observation and actuation latencies. Finally, **Contribution E** focuses on model compression by proposing implicit neural representations (INR)-based scheme for Channel State Information (CSI) compression, integrating quantisation and entropy coding to provide flexible, highly compressed CSI representations suitable for 6G links. Together, these contributions show how model caching, training, and compression can be jointly orchestrated across diverse frameworks to enable scalable, low-latency, and energy-efficient AI services in goal-oriented semantic communication networks.

Keywords

Model management, model caching, model training, model compression.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

6G	Sixth-Generation
ADC	Attention-based Double Compression
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AV	Audio-Visual
AVE	Audio-Visual Event
AVEL	Audio-Visual Event Localization
BS	Base Station
CLS	Classification Token
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CSI	Channel State Information
DI-MDP	Directed-Information-Constrained Markov Decision Processes
DP	Dynamic Programming
FILM	Feature-wise Linear Modulation
INR	Implicit Neural Representations
IoT	Internet of Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MAC	Medium Access Control
MAML	Model-Agnostic Meta-Learning
MA	Multimodal Aggregator
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
ML	Machine Learning
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
MMLM	Multimodal Machine Learning Model
MSE	Mean-Squared Error
NMSE	Normalized Mean-Squared Error
NN	Neural Network
OFDM	Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing
PaMo	At-Least One-Packet Per-Modality
PHY	Physical
QT	Quantitative Target
SemComOps	Semantic Communication Operations
SEMDAS	Semantic Data Acquisition
SGD	Stochastic Gradient Descent
SIREN	Sinusoidal Representation Network
SL	Split Learning
SotA	State-of-the-Art
ToMo	At-Least One-Token Per-Modality
TWI	Temporal Window of Integration
UE	User's Equipment
ViT	Vision Transformer
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The 6G-GOALS project aims to seamlessly integrate Artificial Intelligence (AI) with communication networks to realize semantic and goal-oriented communication paradigms [SDS+24]. This integration embeds meaning, intent, and context directly into transmitted data, enabling the network to convey only goal-relevant information, thereby enhancing efficiency and reducing unnecessary data transmission. Moreover, the project envisions realizing AI services over the network itself, enabling distributed AI inference and training close to end users, powered by novel AI-native network components. This approach transforms the network into an intelligent platform that supports real-time inference, adaptive resource management, and autonomous decision making, distributed across the network hierarchy from centralized cloud infrastructures to edge devices.

By enabling such AI-native functionalities, 6G-GOALS seeks to achieve significant improvements in latency, scalability, privacy, and energy efficiency. This represents a major advance in intelligent, sustainable network architecture design. Central to this vision is the deployment of advanced Machine Learning (ML) models that empower the network and services to intelligently represent, compress, and interpret data through semantic-aware processing.

This deliverable specifically addresses the critical challenge of managing these ML models within the network. It focuses on how to optimally orchestrate their operation and resource allocation to meet dynamic communication objectives and network conditions. In this context, the consortium identifies that the network must handle three key Model Management functions: (i) *Model Caching*, (ii) *Model Training*, and (iii) *Model Compression*.

(i) *Model Caching* consists of strategically storing ML models across protocol layers (e.g., Physical (PHY), Medium Access Control (MAC), data, application) and network locations (e.g., devices, edge, cloud) to optimise latency, energy consumption, and memory usage. It also entails jointly managing the associated data flow, deciding when and where to fetch, place, or update data relative to the cached models. This requires accounting for data locality, relevance, and semantic alignment to ensure that inputs arrive in a form suitable for timely and accurate inference. By tightly integrating data handling with model placement, model caching reduces redundant communication and computation, adapts to heterogeneous network and device capabilities, and improves overall resource efficiency and responsiveness.

(ii) *Model Training* in a networked environment refers to teaching ML models to recognize patterns and perform inference using data distributed across decentralized devices or nodes. It can target network-centric tasks, such as CSI compression at the PHY layer, or higher-level services like adaptive data retrieval and context-aware content delivery. The decentralized setting introduces challenges: Coordinating and synchronizing updates, coping with heterogeneous and often scarce data, and maintaining computational efficiency across distributed resources. Data acquisition further complicates matters because information arrives from different protocol layers (PHY, MAC, data link, application), at various locations (devices, edge, cloud), and with varying quality and volume. This heterogeneity hinders data aggregation and model optimisation and demands protocols and algorithms that operate robustly on partial, fragmented, or noisy datasets. Techniques such as Data Parallelism (splitting data across nodes) and Model Parallelism (splitting model components across nodes) can help balance training load. At the same time, centralized or decentralized coordination mechanisms can help maintain the consistency of the global model if necessary.

(iii) *Model Compression* is a key tool to reduce the size and computational complexity of ML models while targeting to preserve accuracy, enabling deployment in resource-constrained platforms like edge devices. Key techniques include Quantisation (lowering numerical precision), Pruning (eliminating redundant parameters), Knowledge Distillation (transferring capabilities from large teacher models to compact students), and Low-Rank Approximations (factorizing

weight matrices). These methods minimise memory footprint, inference latency, and communication overhead, essential for distributed AI in 6G networks, where ML models must be shared efficiently across PHY, MAC, and application layers and across devices. Model compression can further facilitate model caching and model updates in training by shrinking transfer sizes, accelerating convergence in decentralized training, and supporting real-time predictive inference (e.g., semantic-enabled edge inference) on low-power nodes while reducing possible performance degradation. While aggressive compression risks accuracy loss, hybrid approaches combining multiple techniques with task-specific fine-tuning can help balance efficiency and fidelity, ensuring robust operation across heterogeneous devices.

Together, these functions form the core of Model Management in AI-driven communication networks, ensuring that ML models are stored and accessed efficiently based on contextual demands, trained effectively across distributed infrastructures, and operated with optimised resource utilization through compression techniques.

1.1 Scope and Contributions

In previous deliverables D3.1 [SSC+24] and D3.2 [SGH+25] of WP3, the 6G-GOALS project focused on defining new Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) related to semantic communications and introduced novel goal-oriented, semantic-aware network functionalities within various frameworks of interest. For instance, the consortium addressed the challenge of Semantic Data Acquisition (SEMDAS), wherein heterogeneous data is collected by distributed nodes following a semantic-empowered data retrieval framework, where only information relevant to the requesting node is transmitted by following the definition of a context of interest. Different practical solutions (frameworks, protocols, and algorithms) were proposed around this topic. However, the previous deliverables did not primarily cover how the underlying ML models enabling these frameworks are managed across the network.

This deliverable fills this gap by focusing specifically on *Model Management*, addressing the three critical functions of model caching, training, and compression by properly defining how those ML models are deployed, updated, synchronized, and adapted within distributed and resource-constrained AI-native communication networks. To this end, the deliverable is organized **into five technical contributions**, named A-E, each dedicated to a proposed framework of interest. Within each contribution, we discuss how model management is handled in the context of that specific framework, as management strategies are inherently context-dependent. The considered frameworks cover a range of scenarios relevant to semantic-aware communications and AI services running on the network, spanning multiple network layers. For instance, the SEMDAS problem, discussed in Section 3, pertains to the MAC and application layers, while CSI compression, discussed in Section 7, concerns the PHY layer. Consequently, model management strategies must operate across diverse contexts and perspectives, aiming to optimise overall KPIs of future AI-native communication networks as envisioned for the 6G, which are critical objectives of the 6G-GOALS project.

Table 1-1 gives an overview of how each of the technical contributions relates to the three main functionalities, as well as the Section in the document where they are addressed.

Table 1-1 Model management across different frameworks.

Function	Model Caching	Model Training	Model Compression
<i>Contribution A: Semantic Data Acquisition (SEMDAS) (Section 3)</i>	X		X

<i>Contribution B: Real-Time Multimodal Inference (Section 4)</i>	X		
<i>Contribution C: Efficient Split Training of Transformer Architectures (Section 5)</i>		X	X
<i>Contribution D: Reinforcement Learning for Delayed Constrained Systems (Section 6)</i>		X	X
<i>Contribution E: Compression of Channel State Information (Section 7)</i>		X	

1.2 Disclaimer on Gender Dimension, Equality, Diversity and Responsible AI

The 6G-GOALS project is conducted in full compliance with the equality, diversity, and non-discrimination principles of Horizon Europe and the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking. The research activities implemented for this deliverable, including developing of algorithms, simulations, AI models, and semantic communication mechanisms, are purely technology- and performance-oriented and do not process or rely on personal or demographic attributes (such as gender, ethnicity, age, disability, religion, or socio-economic background).

Where AI/ML techniques are employed, the consortium applies Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) principles and adheres to recognised Trustworthy AI requirements, including fairness, transparency, robustness, and accountability. Dataset selection, synthetic data generation (where applicable), training procedures, and validation protocols are carefully designed to prevent the introduction of unintended bias or discriminatory outcomes.

The consortium remains committed to upholding gender equality and inclusiveness both in research content and in project implementation, ensuring that all scientific outputs, including the present deliverable, and technological developments respect fundamental rights and ethical standards throughout the project lifecycle.

2 List of Contributions and Project-Related Information

In this section, we summarise the key project information and main achievements for each technical contribution (A–E). We focus on the most relevant KPIs and explain how they map to the project’s Quantitative Targets (QTs) (listed in Table 10-1 in the Annex), as well as how they relate to the primary use cases defined in WP2 (D2.1 [SSF+24] and D2.3 [GHS+24]) and to results obtained in other WPs. The QTs reported here are derived from the results in this deliverable and are not intended to be exhaustive, as they do not span all possible use cases and methodological variants. Consistently with D2.1 and D2.3, use cases are grouped into four categories: (i) multimedia-centric use cases, including image, speech, video, and multimodal communication; (ii) task-oriented use cases, such as collaborative robotics and semantic-enabled edge inference; (iii) network-management use cases, including digital twins and semantic state representation for intent-based network management; and (iv) Internet-of-Things (IoT) use cases, addressing semantic aspects of communication among large populations of devices.

Table 2-1 List of contributions regarding model management.

Contribution	KPI	QT	Use Cases in WP2	Link to Other Technical WPs
A	QT3.Communication Overhead	We identify the trade-off between model compression and semantic-relevance detection accuracy. Using Pruning Strategies can reduce the communication overhead for ML model transmission by 40-60% without substantially sacrificing semantic detection accuracy.	Multimedia-centric use cases Task-Oriented use cases Network-management use cases IoT use cases (main)	WP4 / WP5
B	QT2.Timeliness	Using our methodology, edge inference on multimodal data from multiple devices is accelerated by 400–1000 ms with minimal performance loss.	Multimedia-centric use cases Task-Oriented use cases (main) IoT use cases	WP4
C	QT3.Communication Overhead	Our method consistently achieves significantly higher compression gains (often above 80% compared to competitors) without sacrificing model accuracy, including in settings where existing baselines struggle to achieve strong results.	Task-Oriented use cases (main) IoT use-cases	WP4 / WP5
D	QT2 Timeliness	Our base policy method achieves significantly reduced offline training time for compression (more than 100% compared to baseline methods), at the expense of a more computationally	Multimedia-centric use-cases Task-oriented cases (main) IoT use-cases	WP4

		complex online replanning.		
E	QT3.Communication Overhead	Our method formulates the Channel State Information (CSI) compression problem within the framework of Implicit Neural Representations (INR), achieving bit-rate reductions of up to 24.59% while maintaining the same reconstruction quality.	Network-management use cases	WP4 / WP5

3 Contribution A: Semantic Data Acquisition

3.1 Motivation

Previously, the consortium studied the SEMDAS framework [HLL+23], which focuses on efficiently locating and sourcing semantically matched data from distributed nodes (e.g., IoT devices) to enable edge intelligence and minimise unnecessary data transmission, acting as a semantic-aware MAC protocol. Specifically, we investigated schemes in which the nodes collect and transmit data following a random-access protocol activated by *semantic queries*, evaluating their performance and energy efficiency, see our works in [KPH23, TCS+24, KPH25].

In summary, the SEMDAS framework utilizes a *shared semantic embedding or latent space* between an edge server (the requesting node) and distributed devices (the transmitting nodes), where the devices are collecting data from the environment or a physical process of interest. It is important to note that the term embedding space refers to mapping discrete inputs (such as words and categories) to continuous vectors, which is commonly used in the context of Large Language Models, whereas latent space refers to any learned continuous hidden representation (such as from images). We use ‘embedding’ and ‘latent’ interchangeably for generality.

To illustrate how the framework works, consider an end user interested in collecting data related to “cats.” This request arrives at the edge server, which encodes the class “cats” into the semantic space shared between the edge server and the devices, generating a semantic query vector. The edge server broadcasts this vector to nearby devices. Each device encodes its local data into the same semantic space and computes similarity scores relative to the semantic query vector. Devices decide whether to transmit data in the next communication frame based on the magnitude of these similarity scores; that is, on the relevance of their data to the queried concept. As a result, when using random access protocols for uplink transmission (common in IoT applications), collision probabilities become semantically conditioned, whereby devices with relevant data are more likely to contend together, enabling context-aware coordination and reducing irrelevant transmissions.

3.2 Formal Definition

Formally, focusing on a discriminative task, the SEMDAS framework is illustrated in Figure 3-1 and operates as follows. Let \mathbf{q} be a semantic query vector in a semantic (embedding or latent) space \mathcal{S} , representing the semantics of a particular context defined by an end

user request. The edge server, acting as the requesting node, broadcasts \mathbf{q} to all devices. Suppose there are N devices indexed by $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$. Each device i encodes its unlabelled dataset $\mathcal{D}_i = \{x_{i,m}\}_{m=1}^{M_i}$ into the shared semantic space, where each $x_{i,m} \in \mathcal{X}$ is a (data) sample in the input space \mathcal{X} and M_i is the number of samples collected by the i -th device. Observe that this operation can be viewed as a form of model caching.

Each device then computes relevance scores of its samples with respect to \mathbf{q} using a matching function. One way to model this process is to rely on a pre-trained classification model $f: \mathcal{X} \mapsto \mathcal{Y}$ that maps samples into classes. This model can be seen as a composite function $f = E \circ C$, where $E: \mathcal{X} \mapsto \mathcal{S}$ is the encoder component, defining the semantic space, and $C: \mathcal{S} \mapsto \mathcal{Y}$ is the subsequent classification head. Let $match: (\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{S}) \mapsto \mathbb{R}_+$ be a matching score function. Based on the shared semantic space \mathcal{S} , the i -th device measures the relevance of a data sample m to the context \mathbf{q} as:

$$s_{i,m} = match(E(x_{i,m}), \mathbf{q}),$$

where $s_{i,m}$ is the similarity score of the sample $x_{i,m}$. A common approach is to define a threshold semantic relevance score $\tau \in \mathbb{R}_+$. Data points that $s_{i,m} \geq \tau$ are considered relevant and are transmitted following a random-access protocol. This threshold-based strategy allows for flexible, context-aware collision management, where the relevant scores guide the selection process based on semantic similarity and filter out irrelevant data.

In previous deliverables, we have focused on discussing how to select and optimise context-aware collision resolution strategies and matching functions, evaluating KPIs related to throughput and energy efficiency of these procedures [KPH23, TCS+24, KPH25]. However, the consortium did not explicitly discuss Model Management aspects of the SEMDAS framework, which we do next.

Figure 3-1 SEMDAS framework overview.

3.3 Model Management

Typically, the pre-trained ML model f resides at the edge server. The SEMDAS framework could substantially benefit from Continual Learning, which would allow baseline models to be incrementally updated using relevant data transmitted by devices. This would enable the model to adapt over time to evolving environments and dynamic processes under observation. In addition, Federated Learning techniques could be employed to disseminate model updates across distributed devices while preserving data privacy and reducing communication overhead. Nevertheless, we regard training aspects as secondary in this setting, since SEMDAS generally assumes a pre-trained, task-dependent ML model. Rather than committing to a specific task,

we focus on the moral fundamental challenge of efficient protocol-level model management: How can the edge server optimally share its ML model across devices?

A key objective in optimising the SEMDAS framework is to improve its overall performance, energy efficiency, and latency. As discussed in [KPH23, TCS+24, KPH25], we can quantify performance as the proportion of *true positives*, namely, relevant data samples that are correctly identified by devices and successfully delivered to the edge server within the specified context of interest. More precisely, true positives occur when data samples transmitted by devices genuinely belong to the positive class for a given semantic query, and the SEMDAS framework correctly classifies them as such and successfully transmits them.

Maximizing true positives directly enhances system effectiveness by prioritizing the transmission of meaningful information and limiting unnecessary use of communication and computational resources. In this light, performance gains can be achieved through reduced data collisions (yielding more successful transmissions), improved semantic matching functions (leading to more accurate relevance detection and thus higher true-positive rates), and a higher-quality semantic space (with more faithful similarity geometry and a sharper definition of context). Improvements in energy efficiency and latency, in turn, stem from efficient sharing of the encoder to devices, balanced computational loads across matching and inference steps, and a reduction in collision frequency.

While our previous efforts have focused on optimising context-aware collision resolution and the matching function, a key model management challenge in the SEMDAS framework lies in distributing the encoder function E from the edge server to devices. More broadly, this encoder is typically time-varying, denoted as $E(t)$, as it can evolve through retraining or context-dependent fine-tuning, often over large foundation models capable of handling diverse tasks. Distributing such dynamic encoders to devices thus introduces three critical engineering challenges:

1. *Model Size and Complexity*: The encoder's complexity depends heavily on the underlying ML architecture. Transformer-based models, now widely adopted for their expressive capacity, generally contain many parameters (potentially billions), including those encoding long-tail knowledge from pretraining, resulting in a large and potentially unwieldy encoder [PGK+25].
2. *Communication Overhead*: Frequent transmission of the encoder from the edge server to distributed devices is costly and inefficient, especially given the model's possible large size. The sharing frequency must be minimised to preserve bandwidth.
3. *Device Computational Constraints*: Devices often have limited computational and storage capacity, making it challenging to cache and operate large encoder models. Moreover, as the encoder evolves (e.g., through updates or fine-tuning for new contexts), devices must reprocess datasets with updated encoders (re-cache step), adding to the computational burden.

Among these factors, Device Computational Constraints represent the primary bottleneck, as they directly limit the feasible encoder size deployable on-device. In principle, model compression techniques can be applied to reduce the encoder's complexity, thereby lowering communication bandwidth usage and meeting memory requirements. However, excessive compression often deteriorates the quality of the learned semantic space, which in turn impairs semantic relevance detection and reduces true positive rates. This reveals a fundamental trade-off in SEMDAS between model compactness and detection accuracy, governed by the balance between efficiency and representational fidelity.

We illustrate this trade-off in Figure 3-2, considering an image classification task using the CIFAR-10 dataset and the encoder of a LeNet-5 model comprising three convolutional layers (C1: 3→6, C3: 6→16, C5: 16→120 feature maps). The LeNet-5 was trained end-to-end in a supervised manner using cross-entropy loss and Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) with a learning rate of 0.001 and a momentum of 0.9. The dataset was split into 45,000 training images,

5,000 validation images, and 10,000 test images. Training employed early stopping with patience of 5 epochs over the validation accuracy, achieving a test accuracy of 62.04% on the supervised image classification task. In the figure, the pruning rate denotes the percentage of encoder weights zeroed (e.g., 20% pruning rate zeros 20% of weights); this basically represents the amount of bandwidth that can be saved if the model is to be transmitted over a communication channel.

To evaluate how Model Compression can impair semantic relevance detection, we evaluate two unstructured Pruning strategies: *Random Pruning*, which randomly zeros weights of the encoder, and *Magnitude Pruning*, which zeros weights with the smallest magnitudes. To quantify encoder class separability in the semantic space, we compute average intra-class cosine similarity (same-class pairs) and average inter-class cosine similarity (different-class pairs). We then define a *class separation metric* as:

$$\text{AvgClassSeparation} = \text{AvgIntraClassSimilarity} - \text{AvgInterClassSimilarity}.$$

This metric measures how well same-class representations cluster together relative to different-class representations, serving as a proxy metric to measure the detection performance of true positives using the encoder if the matching function is based on cosine similarity. The average is taken with respect to all data samples in the test set.

Figure 3-2 reveals distinct behaviours: Random Pruning shows erratic decay of the class separation metric with peak separation at 0% pruning rate, while Magnitude Pruning initially *improves* separation up to ~65% pruning rate by eliminating noisy small weights. Beyond this threshold, separation degrades rapidly, underscoring the fundamental SEMDAS trade-off: excessive encoder compression sacrifices semantic space quality and true-positive detection accuracy for communication and compute savings.

Figure 3-2 Trade-off between model compression and semantic-relevance detection accuracy.

From this, we observe that a key model management challenge in SEMDAS is identifying *scalable encoder functions* that deliver high-quality semantic spaces (strong generalisation) while remaining lightweight for edge devices and bandwidth-efficient during model sharing from the edge server. We next discuss promising research directions for developing such encoders.

Recently, Hierarchical memories have emerged as a promising solution to address the challenge of sharing Transformer-based encoder models with resource-constrained devices. The authors of [PGK+25] propose a novel pretraining strategy for transformer-based Large Language Models that separates long-tail world knowledge from common reasoning abilities via a

hierarchical memory-augmented architecture. In this approach, a compact base (anchor) model captures general knowledge and reasoning, while a large parametric memory bank stores infrequent, context-specific fact. During both pretraining and inference, only context-relevant memory blocks are selectively retrieved and combined with the anchor model, enhancing efficiency and significantly reducing memory requirements on edge devices. This selective activation of memory parameters also mitigates catastrophic forgetting. Consequently, in the SEMDAS framework, devices can locally store the small anchor model, while the edge server transmits only the relevant memory blocks as needed (given the context), reducing communication overhead and resource consumption.

Another active research direction involves the search for Lightweight Foundation Models (for example, [CPF+25]), which represent a prominent trend in recent ML literature toward parameter-efficient architectures that maintain strong generalization across diverse tasks relevant to wireless networks, for example. These models can be fine-tuned for SEMDAS-specific data types (e.g., environmental sensor streams), enabling deployment on resource-constrained devices. However, their effectiveness remains task-dependent, requiring careful adaptation to semantic relevance detection scenarios.

3.4 Semantic Label Acquisition

In [CPS+24], we introduced a labelling protocol tailored for resource-constrained edge learning scenarios, being related to the SEMDAS framework. In this setting, however, rather than exchanging data samples, a device (the learner) aims to label its locally collected, unlabelled data to train an ML model. The device is connected to an edge server (the teacher) through a bandwidth-limited uplink communication link and a feedback downlink link. Our approach employs Knowledge Distillation [HVD15] as a compression-driven labelling mechanism: the learner obtains soft labels from the teacher's pre-trained model for its local unlabelled dataset. This enables the learner to train compact, efficient models by imitating the teacher's behaviour via supervised learning, thereby reducing computational overhead while preserving performance. Notably, in this framework, the soft labels constitute the downlink feedback from the teacher to the learner, effectively easing the bandwidth requirement in the feedback channel. To further mitigate uplink bandwidth consumption, we introduce a mix-up encoder strategy, where multiple data samples are jointly encoded to reduce communication cost. This is coupled with an Active Learning mechanism to identify and prioritize the most informative samples for transmission.

3.5 Conclusions

In conclusion, the SEMDAS framework advances semantic data acquisition by enabling context-aware coordination across distributed IoT networks, effectively reducing irrelevant transmissions through shared semantic spaces and relevance-driven random access. The consortium has contributed to many works to improve and better define the SEMDAS framework. In that respect, it was identified that model management, particularly caching and compression, emerges as a critical frontier to address challenges in encoder distribution such as model size, communication overhead, and device-level constraints, while preserving the semantic quality necessary for accurate detection, as illustrated by the pruning trade-off curve in Figure 3-2. A key open challenge lies in developing scalable encoder architectures, which may be addressed through the concept of hierarchical memories [PGK+25], enabling selective caching of context-relevant components in conjunction with a lightweight anchor model. Furthermore, model compression using lightweight Foundation Models [CPF+25] and Knowledge Distillation [CPS+24], as demonstrated in the Semantic Label Acquisition problem, can efficiently reduce downlink feedback and mitigate communication bottlenecks; however, such techniques must be applied judiciously to preserve the integrity of the semantic space. Overall, effective caching and compression strategies represent essential enablers for scalable, privacy-preserving, and semantically driven data retrieval in future AI-native communication networks.

4 Contribution B: Real-Time Multimodal Inference

4.1 Motivation

The 6G-GOALS project develops future wireless networks to support new, emerging AI services like real-time inference. In applications such as autonomous driving and cyber-physical systems, there are scenarios in which data streams from multiple modalities (e.g., audio, video) arrive at heterogeneous rates from diverse devices or *sources* at a central location for processing. Multimodal Machine Learning Models (MMLMs) serve as key enablers, fusing these sensor streams to extract real-time insights [LZM24]. However, a core engineering challenge for enabling real-time inference upon these multimodal streams lies in managing asynchronous data arrivals from distinct sources, each with unique infrastructure and modality-dependent data representations. Consequently, each source exhibits source- and modality-specific delay distributions, while MMLM inference demands stringent latency constraints. Herein, we interpret this as a model caching problem, where asynchronous multimodal data subject to different delay distributions arriving at a centralized location must be effectively synchronized and processed to perform inference using a cached MMLM. Timely and accurate fusion of these heterogeneous streams is thus essential for reliable real-time inference.

Motivated by this context, we study the challenge of handling multimodal streams from diverse sources, where each source transmits a distinct modality subject to modality-specific communication uncertainties. As illustrated in Figure 4-1, our framework focuses on an Audio-Visual (AV) distributed multimodal system where each source transmits a modality-specific sensor stream over independent channels affected by stochastic communication delays. A Multimodal Aggregator (MA) collects these streams and hosts a pre-trained, cached AV-MMLM for real-time inference. In studying this framework, the fundamental research question we are interested in is: How can a real-time inference system accommodate asymmetric, uncertain communication delays in multimodal streams while preserving *temporal coherence* across modalities, thereby ensuring accurate fusion and reliable multimodal AI services in dynamic wireless environments?

Figure 4-1 A distributed AV system, where unimodal auditory and visual data, covering overlapping AVEs, are streamed to an MA. The limitations of SotA approaches are demonstrated through two adverse scenarios.

Here, *temporal coherence* refers to the alignment and preservation of consistent temporal relationships across multimodal data streams. Analogously, the human brain faces the same challenge of maintaining temporal coherence to form a meaningful perception of reality. For example, auditory signals (~150 ms neural delay) and visual signals (~50 ms) traverse distinct pro-

cessing pipelines and propagate at different speeds, yet the brain has evolved specialized neural mechanisms, such as temporal binding and cross-modal synchronization, to resolve these discrepancies and achieve perceptual unity [BK02].

State-of-the-Art (SotA) solutions to this problem (e.g., [LHR+21]) typically employ non-blocking inference strategies based on two key assumptions: (1) their strategy is based on choosing a *reference modality*, often the one arriving fastest, and, therefore, it arrives quickly enough to trigger inference once its full *context window*, the minimum data volume required by the AV-MMLM for accurate processing, is received, and (2) *offline, human-curated profiles* characterize expected source-coding and communication conditions, where, at runtime, the strategy detects the operating regime and adapts using this predefined profiling dictionary. However, one can argue that these assumptions introduce several practical limitations, of which the most important ones are mentioned next. First, they require constant and reliable availability of the reference modality, which is often unrealistic in dynamic or lossy networks. Second, their rigid temporal dependence on the reference modality constrains the exploitation of partial observations, limiting early or subtle decision-making. Third, if there is a need to switch the reference modality to cope with dynamic degradation (e.g., network fluctuations), this would demand extensive re-training and incur additional memory overhead, ultimately reducing flexibility and scalability.

To ground these limitations, Figure 4-1 depicts a canonical bimodal AV distributed system, where unimodal auditory and visual streams are captured by two separate sources, each independently streaming continuous data to the MA under independent channels statistically characterized by modality-specific communication delay uncertainties. At the MA, a pre-trained AV-MMLM supports tasks such as the Audio-Visual Event Localization (AVEL) task [TSL+18], where an *AV Event* (AVE) is both audible and visible within the scene. In line with common practice (Figure 4-1, *left*), the auditory stream is typically chosen as the reference modality because of its relatively low bandwidth compared to the visual stream, and SotA methods often assume near-instantaneous audio reception. However, even for low-bandwidth audio, one can show that communication uncertainties can substantially distort how the MA observes and synchronizes multimodal data. In a moderately adverse delay scenario (Figure 4-1, *middle*), the transmission time of the reference modality becomes comparable to that of the non-reference modality, causing considerable inference latency because the system stalls until full reference arrival; as the inter-modality delay shrinks, the effectiveness of SotA approaches degrades. In an extreme adverse scenario (Figure 4-1, *right*), the delays of both modalities converge or become comparable, making reference selection ambiguous and effectively collapsing the performance of these SotA methods. Such situations naturally arise under highly variable network conditions and heterogeneous source resources, factors that are often idealized away or ignored in prior work.

4.2 A Neuro-Inspired Solution

In our recent work [CSP+25], we have proposed a novel non-blocking inference method inspired by plausible mechanisms on how the human brain integrates and binds streams of information, while avoiding the assumptions made previously. Specifically, we use the notion of Temporal Windows of Integration (TWIs), adaptive temporal windows hypothesised to underlie how the human brain achieves temporal coherence across the senses [BK02]. Due to this, our approach is referred to as *the neuro-inspired or bio-inspired wrapper*, where the word wrapper highlights that the non-blocking inference method “wraps” a pre-trained AV-MMLM, governing how it consumes data and produces predictions. Unlike SotA methods that often disregard communication uncertainties, while designing our wrapper, we also explicitly model and incorporate these uncertainties as a fundamental system component, allowing us to leverage them as predictive information to optimise the TWIs, avoiding assuming fixed profiling of those aspects. More importantly, by introducing auxiliary mechanisms that foster temporal coherence and statistically optimising the TWIs based on modelling communication uncertainties, we gain finer control over inference without needing assumptions such as a reference modality or offline profiling.

In the following, we summarize how our neuro-inspired solution works; details can be found in [CSP+25]. From the system shown in Figure 4-1, it is important to note that data sources transmit *packets* composed of multiple samples, whereas AV-MMLMs consume data as *tokens*, groupings of samples that form semantically meaningful units for the model. Therefore, data has three hierarchical levels of representations: samples (fundamental in acquiring data), packets (for communication), and tokens (for inference). Consequently, the wrapper's critical function is to align modality-specific packet streams, each affected by distinct delay uncertainties, to generate temporally consistent token sequences that enable reliable multimodal fusion and inference while basic processing occurs on a sample-level.

To realize this and align with WP3 goals, we introduce an independent per-packet communication delay model for each modality. Based on this model, our wrapper operates using a TWI-based clock. Within each integration period, the wrapper collects packets, binds them coherently, and extracts or updates features according to the AV-MMLM pipeline and the new collected and temporally coherent data. At the end of the integration period, which serves as our inference deadline, the wrapper outputs a prediction using the updated information while buffering/caching information that will be useful in the future. We optimise the TWI length based on the average statistics of the delay distributions and propose two methods: the At-Least One-Packet Per-Modality (**PaMo**) TWI, which ensures that, on average, at least one packet per modality is received before inference is triggered by the end of the integration period; and the At-Least One-Token Per-Modality (**ToMo**) TWI, which guarantees that, on average, each modality contributes at least one token before inference is triggered.

4.3 Experimental Results

For experiments, we consider the AVEL dataset in a fully supervised setting [TSL+18]. The dataset comprises 4097 10-secs video observations, partitioned into training 80%, validation 10%, and test 10% subsets. Each observation is segmented into 10 non-overlapping 1-sec tokens, each annotated with noisy labels across 28 AVE plus a background class denoting silence. As a baseline, we adopt the simplest AV-MLMM from [TSL+18], which achieves 67.20% average test accuracy on the AVEL task when both modalities' streams are fully available.

Figure 4-2 illustrates the performance of our neuro-inspired wrapper design against SotA approaches that rely on a reference modality paradigm while choosing parameters to meet practical conditions. Specifically, we assume that audio is being transmitted using enhanced Machine-Type Communication specifications while video transmission uses enhanced Mobile Broadband specifications; further details can be found in [CSP+25]. It is important to note that in each subfigure, we are controlling the delay distribution of audio by changing the average Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), while the visual delay distribution remains fixed. Particularly, Figure 4-2 (a) refers to the case in which the video is the reference modality, as the delay distribution of audio is excessively impaired by a low SNR value, while the opposite occurs in Figure 4-2 (c), where the audio is the reference modality. In Figure 4-2 (b), the delay distributions of both modalities are matched, so there is an ambiguity in choosing which modality is the reference one. Due to this change in delay distributions, the amount of information received in each subfigure changes, which justifies why the SotA curves change. The SotA baseline curves are defined as the accuracy achieved for the first inference round of using the AV-MMLM after fully receiving the reference modality.

In the figure, given that auditory information is generally more discriminative than visual cues in the AVEL dataset, we can observe that the SotA methods achieve their highest accuracy relative to the amount of data available of 64.87% in Figure 4-2 (c). Correspondingly, as the auditory packet rate increases with higher values of the average audio SNR, $\bar{\gamma}_a$, the accuracy of our PaMo and ToMo variants exhibits a slightly steeper accuracy improvement from Figure 4-2 (a) and Figure 4-2 (b) to Figure 4-2 (c), where each variant represents different strategies for selecting the TWI. To quantify the accuracy-latency trade-off, we use the SotA accuracy as a

baseline and define a tolerable accuracy loss of 5% absolute, indicated by the dashed red horizontal line. Within this threshold, our method can reduce latency by (1055, 490, 426) ms across the three scenarios, with the greatest gain when audio lags, reflecting its higher discriminative power. The main difference between PaMo and ToMo variants lies in their computational and inference profiles: ToMo triggers the AV-MMLM pipeline less frequently, while PaMo provides finer-grained accuracy-latency control.

Figure 4-2 Average accuracy over the test set as a function of average end-to-end inference latency, comparing our neuro-inspired wrapper to SotA approaches across varying auditory SNR values $\bar{\gamma}_a$ and fixed visual SNR $\bar{\gamma}_v = 0$ [dB]. We denote $\bar{T}_s = \mathbb{E}[T_{i,s}]$ for $s \in \{a, v\}$ as the average total transmission time per modality. The “- - -” lines indicate a 5%-absolute-drop-margin of accuracy w.r.t. SotA.

4.4 Conclusions

Overall, our neuro-inspired paradigm dynamically adapts to communication delay uncertainties and effectively explores the accuracy-latency trade-off curve, unlike reference-modality-based SotA methods. More details can be found in [CSP+25]. We emphasize the critical importance of this work in enabling real-time inference on multimodal data streams transmitted over communication networks, serving as an effective model caching technique for temporally handling data to fit the expectations of cached MMLMs. This capability is essential for establishing new types of AI services and preparing networks to efficiently handle the unique demands of real-time AI applications.

5 Contribution C: Efficient Split Training of Transformer-Based Architectures

5.1 Motivation

Split Learning (SL) is a distributed training paradigm in which a Neural Network (NN) is partitioned between a client and a server, enabling privacy-preserving computation while leveraging large-scale models. By relaxing the strict separation between on-device inference and server-

side training, SL allows model designers to jointly optimise client-side computation and server-side processing for task-specific performance. However, a key challenge arises from the need to exchange large intermediate activations and gradients between the two parties. In standard SL, the dimensionality of intermediate activations is fixed and independent of the input complexity. This may waste computation and transmission energy since full-size activations are exchanged even when compressed representations would be sufficient for training. This limitation becomes more pronounced as models scale and as applications demand frequent boundary-crossing communication during both forward and backward passes.

Practically, we may be interested in adaptive transmission protocols able to select the appropriate number of activations to send based on the transmission power we are willing to commit. This translates to a client with variable-size outputs, where the number of required bits can be adjusted to meet external bandwidth constraints. To achieve this with standard NNs, representative approaches often employ autoencoders or additional compression networks. However, within the scope of this WP, we are interested in compressing the activation without having to train additional networks or perform fine-tuning.

In particular, we focus on SL schemes implemented via transformer NN models, which have been originally proposed in the natural language processing field but have become the de facto model of choice for most applications, including computer vision (Vision Transformers, ViTs [WHS+21]). Transformers work by pre-processing the input with a step known as tokenization, which converts the input into a sequence of (vector-valued) symbols known as tokens. For example, in ViTs, images are split into non-overlapping blocks, known as image patches, which are then projected to vectors. This sequence is then processed by a series of blocks, the most important of which is the multi-head attention layer, which updates the embeddings by linearly combining all tokens in the sequence. Importantly, this operation acts by pairwise comparisons, making it amenable to modifications in the input sequence, such as reordering or removal of specific tokens. Having a set of tokens as activations allows us to operate on and transmit them more easily than multidimensional tensors.

In the context of WP3, we proposed a dynamic approach to reduce the activation size and hence the required transmission power needed, named Attention-based Double Compression (ADC) [APL+25]. The proposed approach leverages the properties of Transformer-based models to perform a two-step compression: first, it performs a dynamic clustering that merges similar sample activations within the batch; second, it reduces the dimensionality of these merged activations by retaining only the most relevant tokens and discarding the rest. This also impacts the gradients communicated back by the server, which are naturally compressed without additional approximation. Compared to similar approaches, our merging proposal focuses on the attention scores of the features themselves instead of the labels, boosting the compression ratio by allowing the merging of samples with different labels without degrading classification accuracy. In the context of distributed and bandwidth-limited learning scenarios, such as edge-to-cloud training pipelines, this represents a significant step toward privacy-aware, adaptive, and communication-efficient transformer models. The proposed mechanism provides a controllable trade-off between bandwidth, accuracy, and computational load, enabling practical deployment of ViT-based split learning systems under real-world constraints.

5.2 Methodology

We describe the setup in the context of supervised computer vision, although the methodology is applicable, with small modifications, to any scenario in which a transformer model is used. We assume a transmitter, referred to as the client, that is jointly updated with a server. To this end, it must communicate the activations of the training samples to the server, which responds with the gradients that must be applied on the client to perform the alignment update. In the communications stage, no additional NNs are used.

Figure 5-1 Visualisation of the proposed method. The batch activations are merged based on cluster similarity. These clusters are computed over the attention scores of the class tokens. Then, of the merged activations, only the most important tokens are kept, and the rest are discarded. The resulting activations are sent to a remote server to complete the training step.

After the tokenization step, a set of images $x = \{x_i\}_{i=1}^N$ can be represented as a set of tokens, including the image tokens and a special token known as a classification token (CLS token, which is used to make predictions at the receiver's end using a classification head). The full SL pipeline is described as two components applied sequentially:

$$y = (C \circ S)(x),$$

where C and S are the client and the server, respectively. Following [TCS+22], the SL procedure comprises three steps:

- 1 *Client Forward Pass*: Given a generic samples-labels tuple (x, y) , the client produces the activation set as $z = C(x)$ and sends it to the server along with the label.
- 2 *Server Update*: The server receives z , continues the computations, and produces the output $\bar{y} = S(z)$. Such output is used to calculate the loss and the associated gradients. The server transmits the backward gradients g to the client for the alignment.
- 3 *Client Update*: The client receives the gradients g and uses the chain rule to update the local model parameters.

The compression is performed only on the client side. First, the method performs batch compression: it computes the attention scores of the class token in the last local transformer block. These attention vectors capture how each sample distributes importance across its tokens. Using these vectors, the original batch of size N is clustered into T groups based on attention similarity ($T < N$). The activations within each cluster are merged into a single centroid, effectively reducing the batch size from N to T . Labels are merged accordingly to form soft targets.

Second, for each merged activation (which contains t tokens), the method performs token selection: only the top- k most informative tokens, those with the highest attention values based on the cluster centroids, are retained and transmitted ($k < t$). All other tokens are discarded, reducing both the transmitted activations and the corresponding backward gradients. All the details about the two steps can be found in [APL+25].

Figure 5-2 Visualisation of clusters obtained when retaining 10% of the information.

This leads to a two-dimensional compression, in which not only the number of samples is reduced (from N to T), but also the effective number of tokens (from t to k). The result is a communication reduction proportional to the product of the batch-compression and token-compression ratios ($N/B \cdot k/t$). Experimental results demonstrate that this approach maintains high accuracy even under aggressive compression ratios, significantly outperforming baselines that rely on single-dimension compression. The scheme requires **no** architectural changes or auxiliary compressors and integrates seamlessly into standard split-ViT training.

5.3 Experimental Results

The experimental evaluation of the proposed algorithm is divided into two broad parts. In the first part, the proposed compression technique is tested against other similar methods. In the second part, the method is studied to understand how its components and parameters affect the final results.

Main results: For the first part, we tested the methods on the Food101 dataset [BGV14] using DeiT-T and DeiT-S ViTs [TCD+21]. As baselines, we selected Top- K and RandTop K [ZCL+23], which select the tokens to transmit based on their magnitudes. The selected tokens are transmitted along with their indices to allow the server to reconstruct the sparse tensor. C3-SL [HCW22] is a batch compression technique that takes activations as groups and compresses them together into a single one using circular convolution. The compressed activations are recovered on the receiver side using superposition. Lastly, BottleNet++ [EEP19] compresses each token using lightweight feed-forward networks immediately before and after the split point, while Base is the standard training in which no compression is performed. For each method, the final compression ratio depends on its hyperparameters. Results are shown in Figure 5-3.

Figure 5-3 Results obtained using DeiT-T (left) and DeiT-S (right).

Among the evaluated methods, our proposal is the only approach that consistently preserves high accuracy across both architectures and datasets, achieving good results even when aggressive compression ratios are used. In particular, it provides the best results in the low-compression ratio regime, where most competing approaches exhibit severe performance degradation.

Ablations: The first parameter we test is the splitting point, which, given a ViT, is the layer where the client ends, and the server begins (and where the compression is performed).

Figure 5-4 Results obtained using DeiT-T with a compression factor of 0.5.

The results are shown in Figure 5-4. It shows that our approach improves the results when the splitting point is placed deeper in the model (higher splitting point). This happens because in the deeper layers, the class token, which is used for merging the activations, is more semantically informative.

The dimension of the batch size plays a huge role in compression algorithms for SL. Figure 5-5 shows how its selection affects the final results for each method. It shows that while performance improves with larger batches, our proposal remains stable even at smaller batch sizes. We attribute this improvement to the increased diversity of samples within larger batches, which allows the clustering algorithm to identify clusters with more aligned activations (specifically regarding their attention score distributions).

Figure 5-5 How the final accuracy is affected by the batch size for different compression ratios ξ .

5.4 Conclusions

The proposed ADC scheme demonstrates that meaningful communication savings can be achieved in SL setups without altering the underlying ViT architecture or compromising performance. By leveraging attention patterns as a principled indicator of sample and token relevance, the method introduces an efficient way to reduce both batch size and sequence length before transmission. This results in a substantial reduction of forward and backward communication costs while preserving accuracy across datasets and compression settings. Overall, the approach provides a practical and scalable solution for deploying transformer-based models in bandwidth-limited, edge-to-cloud training scenarios, and highlights the broader potential of attention-driven mechanisms for adaptive compression in distributed learning.

6 Contribution D: Reinforcement Learning for Delayed Constrained Systems

6.1 Motivation

In modern AI-native networks and communication-constrained cyber-physical systems, one of the central challenges is not only how to make optimal decisions but how to manage the models that underpin those decisions. Systems increasingly operate under tight constraints on bandwidth, latency, memory, and computation, meaning that the underlying decision models must be trained efficiently, represented compactly, and updated continuously as new information arrives. In the context of semantically encoding data sources, a key topic in the 6G-GOALS project, Directed-Information-Constrained Markov Decision Processes (DI-MDPs) offer a natural way to formalize this trade-off, because directed information measures the communication load required for control. In this view, MDPs model control operations realized at a receiver using information communicated by a transmitter. However, solving DI-MDPs exactly requires working with a continuous belief state [HCS25a], which behaves like a high-dimensional model whose full representation is computationally unrealistic. If one attempts to train such a model directly, the memory cost explodes, and the dynamic programming recursion becomes unsustainable. This is precisely where model management becomes critical: we need a principled way to compress, approximate, update, and deploy the model so that it can be trained offline but still refined online. The core motivation of our work is to design a model-centric pipeline that integrates approximation, training, compression, and refinement in a stable and scalable manner.

6.2 Methodology

Our methodology treats DI-MDPs jointly as a model-training and model-compression problem. In particular, we formalize DI in terms of the conditional mutual information, denoted by $I(\cdot; \cdot | \cdot)$, and defined through the following expression:

$$I(x_t; y_t | y^{t-1}) = \mathbb{E} \left(\frac{\mu_t(dy_t | y^{t-1}, x_t)}{v_t(dy_t | y^{t-1})} \right),$$

where x_t denotes the noiseless information being generated by a discrete Markov source at a transmitter at time t , while y_t represents the information received after being communicated over a channel and passed over a source encoder-decoder pipeline. The operator $\mathbb{E}(\cdot)$ denotes the expected value. The mutual information is conditioned on the previously received information y^{t-1} . Moreover, $\mu_t(\cdot)$ denotes the control function of the MDP process and $v_t(\cdot)$ the control or action, for all $t = \{0, 1, \dots, N\}$. The expression above can be used to train a controller at the receiver, where minimising this quantity subject to a fidelity constraint, such as the single-letter distortion $\mathbb{E}[\rho_t(x_t, y_t)] \leq D_t$, encourages the controller to be “information frugal,” relying only on essential state features.

Training such a controller would require a model training that involves an offline phase where we cast the exact Dynamic Programming (DP) representation to minimise DI-MDP, in terms of Q-factor representation. Following a Reinforcement Learning methodology, the Q-factor representation is given as:

$$Q_t^*(b_t, \mu_t) = \mathbb{E} \left[\left(\frac{\mu_t(dy_t|y^{t-1}, x_t)}{v_t(dy_t|y^{t-1})} \right) - s_t(\rho_t - D_t) + \min_{\mu_{t+1}} Q_{t+1}^*(b_{t+1}, \mu_{t+1}) \right],$$

where $s_t > 0$ is a Lagrangian multiplier associated with the distortion penalty $D_t > 0$ of the DI-MDP, for any $t = \{0, 1, \dots, N\}$. This representation can be viewed as the full “uncompressed model,” which is too large to store or be trained directly because the belief state b_t lives in a continuous space. Instead of training this full model, we perform offline model compression by discretizing the belief space into a compact grid \bar{B}_t and training a short-horizon approximation $Q_{N_s}^{\bar{\pi}}$ only over a rolling window $N_s \ll N$. This creates a compressed base model that captures essential dynamics without storing the entire belief space. The offline step effectively performs model training with controlled complexity, reducing the offline cost to $O(N_s n)$ from $O(Nn)$, where n is the number of quantisation levels and $O(\cdot)$ denotes the big-oh notation. Once this compressed model is trained, we move to online model refinement via rollout, where the improved control action is obtained by minimising an approximate Q-factor. Each rollout step can be interpreted as a local fine-tuning update, like online learning: the model is refined on-the-fly using real belief trajectories instead of the full training set. Finally, through repeated rollout, we regenerate a more representative belief grid \hat{B}_t from empirical data and retrain a more accurate compressed model. This creates a full model-management cycle: train \rightarrow compress \rightarrow refine \rightarrow retrain \rightarrow deploy [HCS25b].

6.3 Experimental Results

Our simulations highlight these model-management concepts in action. We evaluate the framework on a binary Markov system under Hamming distortion, comparing (1) the full approximate DP method, (2) the approximated DP model with rollout refinement presented in [HCS25a], and (3) the repeated-rollout retrained model here discussed. In Figure 6-1, we report the *stage-wise information-theoretic cost*, i.e., the per-time-step directed information term $I(x_t; y_t | y^{t-1})$, which quantifies the amount of state information conveyed by the control action under the communication constraint. The results show that the compressed model, once refined online, not only matches but surpasses the performance of the full discretization method proposed in [HCS25a]. Stage-wise directed information costs decrease significantly, demonstrating that a smaller, compressed model, when continually refined, can outperform a larger, static one, reducing the communication load required for control.

This is the same insight that drives modern ML practices such as Knowledge Distillation and lightweight model deployment. The time-consumption results further support this: the compressed offline model is trained far more efficiently, and because its dimensionality is lower, it requires substantially less Random Access Memory (RAM) consumption. This comes at the expense of the online phase, which is substantially more computationally intensive compared to the prior art, as shown in Figure 6-2.

The significant gains in the offline phase allow us to explore richer belief refinements and perform more frequent online updates. When repeated rollout is deployed, the model adapts to the actual distribution of belief states observed during operation, effectively retraining on relevant data and improving performance even further. The outcome is a dynamic model that becomes more accurate the more it is used, an ideal property for systems that must operate under uncertain, changing conditions.

Figure 6-1 Illustration of the stage-wise information-theoretic cost and time consumption comparison.

Figure 6-2 Time consumption comparison between the offline and online phases of [HCS25a] and this work.

6.4 Conclusions

This work demonstrates how DI-MDPs can be tackled not just as a control problem but as a model management problem, involving careful decisions about how models are trained, compressed, stored, and updated. The combination of rolling-horizon approximation (model compression), offline Q-factor training (model learning), online rollout (model updating), and repeated rollout (model retraining) creates a unified framework that is scalable, adaptable, and resource aware. These principles resonate strongly with the challenges faced in 6G semantic communication systems (AI-native networks), networked autonomy, and AI-native control loops, where models must operate reliably with limited information and computational budgets. Through this perspective, we show that large and intractable information-state models can be transformed into manageable, high-performance decision engines. From a semantic/goal-oriented communications perspective, the distortion constraint can be interpreted as a task-fidelity

requirement: the controller does not need the full state information, but only the minimal information sufficient to achieve the control goal within a target performance level. Minimising directed information, therefore, acts as a principled semantic compression mechanism, limiting communication to task-relevant state features while discarding irrelevant details.

The final takeaway is that model compression plus online refinement is not merely a computational shortcut; it is a powerful model-management strategy that ensures performance improves as the system interacts with the environment. This positions our approach as a solid foundation for future work in robust, communication-efficient, and adaptive decision-making architectures.

7 Contribution E: Compression of Channel State Information

7.1 Motivation

In this section, we focus on the problem of CSI compression, entailing its feedback and reconstruction at the PHY layer using ML models. Traditional ML-based CSI compression techniques rely on viewing the channel matrix as a high-dimensional discrete object, such as an image, tensor, or sequence, to be encoded and reconstructed. This perspective inherently couples the model architecture to specific antenna configurations, bandwidths, and grid resolutions, making generalisation difficult and limiting scalability as system dimensions grow. Furthermore, conventional encoder–decoder networks produce latent vectors that lack explicit physical meaning, resulting in representations that are brittle to distribution shifts induced by mobility, frequency selectivity, or environmental changes. These constraints are increasingly problematic in modern multi-antenna systems, where feedback overhead must be reduced drastically without sacrificing the fidelity required for beamforming and sensing.

Figure 7-1 Illustration of different CSI feedback methodologies for an MIMO-OFDM system.

Figure 7-1 illustrates different CSI compression methodologies for a Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO)-Orthogonal-Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) system: (top) the conventional approach using an encoder-decoder model, (middle) an approach using Implicit Neural Representations (INR) to represent each CSI compression, and (bottom) our proposal based on INR combined with a shared base network.

As shown in the figure, INR provides a fundamentally different modelling paradigm that addresses these limitations [WZS+22]. By treating CSI as a continuous function of spatial and

frequency coordinates, INRs replace large discrete tensors with compact neural fields whose parameters encode the underlying physical structure of the channel. This yields strong interpolation and generalisation capabilities, allowing the same model to operate seamlessly across different antenna layouts and sub-carrier densities. Moreover, INR frameworks enable compression through lightweight modulation codes that condition the network, reducing feedback to a small set of task-adaptive parameters rather than full reconstructed matrices. These properties make INRs an attractive and forward-looking solution for CSI compression, offering efficiency, robustness, and scalability within dynamic and heterogeneous wireless environments.

7.2 The Architecture of the CSI-INR Scheme

Figure 7-2 illustrates the overall architecture and training procedure of the proposed CSI-INR scheme. Figure 7-2 (a) shows the basic building blocks of the model: a *shared base network* initialized via meta-learning and a *CSI modulation network* that maps each CSI sample H^i to a low-dimensional modulation codeword M^i . This codeword is then transformed into per-layer Feature-wise Linear Modulation (FiLM) parameters $\phi^i = \{(\gamma_1^i, \eta_1^i), \dots, (\gamma_{L_t}^i, \eta_{L_t}^i)\}$, which scale and shift the intermediate features of a stack of Sinusoidal Representation Network (SIREN) layers, producing a sample-specific neural function $\hat{H}^i = f_\theta(x, \phi_i)$ that reconstructs the CSI matrix from its coordinates. Figure 7-2 (a) also shows that the modulation vectors are quantised and entropy-coded to generate compact feedback bits. Figure 7-2 (b) depicts the meta-learning training loop. A shared base network with parameters θ is iteratively optimised together with the modulation codewords for many CSI samples. In the inner loop, for each CSI matrix H^i , its modulation vector M^i is updated by gradient descent to minimise reconstruction MSE while keeping θ fixed. In the outer loop, after several inner steps over a batch of samples, the base network parameters θ are updated, while the modulation vectors are kept fixed. This alternating optimisation converges to a meta-learned initialization θ^* that allows fast adaptation in a few inner steps and highly compressed CSI feedback via the learned modulations.

Figure 7-2 The architecture of the CSI-INR scheme.

7.2.1 Base INR Network

The Base INR network is a shared coordinate-based neural model that learns to map every antenna-sub-carrier coordinate in the CSI matrix to its corresponding channel value. It begins by transforming each 2-D coordinate through a Fourier feature layer, which injects rich high-

frequency components and allows the network to represent the rapid phase changes typical of multipath wireless channels. After this spectral encoding, the signal passes through a stack of SIREN layers, whose oscillatory activations are well suited for modelling the smooth-but-non-linear variations of CSI across space and frequency. A final linear layer converts the learned representation into the real and imaginary parts of the channel. Because this base network is meta-learned and shared across all users, it acts as a universal functional prior for CSI, requiring only a small modulation vector per user to adapt it to a specific channel instance. In this way, the Base INR network provides the foundational structure that enables CSI-INR to achieve highly compact yet accurate CSI reconstruction.

7.2.2 CSI Modulation

The CSI modulation module is responsible for converting each individual CSI matrix into a compact vector of modulation codes. Instead of training a separate neural network for every CSI instance, this module distils the unique characteristics of each channel sample into a small, learnable codeword. This codeword is produced by a lightweight Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP)-based network that takes the CSI data as input and outputs a set of modulation parameters. These parameters are not used to replace the weights of the base network; rather, they serve as a set of selectors or controllers that influence how the shared base INR network behaves for a specific CSI instance. As a result, the CSI modulation module effectively bridges raw CSI data and the implicit neural representation at extremely low dimensionality.

Once the modulation codeword is generated, it is used to adjust the intermediate activations of multiple SIREN layers inside the base INR network through FiLM. In practice, this means the modulation vector provides a set of scale and shift values that dynamically reshape the feature flow inside each layer of the base network. By applying different modulation patterns, the shared model can flexibly represent the channel structure of many different CSI samples without re-training or exchanging a large number of weights. This design greatly enhances compression efficiency: only the small modulation codeword needs to be transmitted, and it remains highly quantisable and robust to low-bit representations. Through this mechanism, the CSI modulation module enables efficient, adaptive, and fine-grained personalization of the base INR network for each user's channel realization.

7.2.3 Training Strategy

The training strategy of CSI-INR follows a meta-learning, Model-Agnostic Meta-Learning (MAML)-like scheme with two nested loops: an inner loop that optimises the modulation codeword for each CSI sample, and an outer loop that updates the shared base INR network. In the inner loop, for each CSI instance, the modulation vector is initialized (e.g., to zero) and then refined by a few steps of gradient descent while keeping the base network parameters fixed. Each step moves the modulation codeword in the direction that reduces the reconstruction MSE between the original CSI matrix and the one reconstructed by the modulated base network. A typical inner-loop update for the modulation codeword of the i -th sample at step j is

$$M_i^{(j)} = M_i^{(j-1)} - \alpha \nabla_{M_i^{(j-1)}} \mathcal{L}_{mse}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, M_i^{(j-1)}, d_i),$$

where α is the inner-loop learning rate, $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ denotes the current base network parameters, and d_i is the pair consisting of the coordinates and CSI matrix of the i -th sample.

After several inner-loop steps have produced updated modulation vectors for a batch of CSI samples, the outer loop updates the base network parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ by minimising the same Mean-Squared Error (MSE) loss but now with the modulation vectors held fixed. Intuitively, the base network learns an initialization that can be quickly adapted to any new CSI instance via a small number of inner-loop updates on its modulation codeword. This alternating optimisation of modulation vectors (inner loop) and base network parameters (outer loop) continues until conver-

gence. The result is a meta-learned base INR network that supports fast per-instance adaptation and allows CSI to be represented compactly through short modulation codewords, which can later be quantised and entropy-coded for efficient feedback.

7.3 Quantisation and Entropy Coding

The quantisation and entropy coding module further compresses the modulation codewords produced by CSI-INR, enabling extremely low-bit CSI feedback without noticeable performance loss. After the inner-loop optimisation produces a modulation vector for each CSI sample, this vector is first passed through a simple uniform quantiser, which maps each element to one of a small number of discrete levels, e.g., 3-8 bits. A key finding is that these modulation vectors are surprisingly quantisable: even aggressive quantisation with only a few bits per element results in only minor degradation in reconstruction accuracy. This property arises because the learned modulation codes lie in a smooth, structured space shaped by the meta-trained base INR network.

After quantisation, the discrete modulation symbols are further compressed using entropy coding, specifically arithmetic coding. By estimating the empirical distribution of quantised modulation values from the training set, the entropy encoder can assign shorter bit sequences to frequent symbols and longer sequences to rare ones. This step yields additional bit savings of up to 24.6% without affecting reconstruction performance. Entropy decoding and dequantisation at the Base Station (BS) are exact inverses of the operations at the User's Equipment (UE), ensuring lossless recovery of the quantised modulation vectors before they are fed into the base INR network for CSI reconstruction. Together, quantisation and entropy coding make CSI-INR highly suitable for practical feedback scenarios where bandwidth is extremely limited, achieving superior rate-distortion performance compared with prior deep-learning-based CSI compression schemes.

7.4 CSI Feedback Strategy

The CSI feedback strategy in CSI-INR is built on the idea that the transmitter (the UE) and receiver (the BS) share the same base INR network, so only the modulation codewords need to be fed back. On the UE side, given a new CSI matrix and the meta-learned base network, the UE runs a small number of inner-loop gradient steps to optimise its modulation vector, starting from an initialization such as zero. This modulation vector is then optionally quantised and entropy-coded into a very short bitstream and transmitted over the feedback link. Because the base network and modulation network architectures are known and synchronized at both ends, there is no need to send network weights or full feature maps, which indicates that only this compact codeword is fed back. At the BS side, the received bitstream is entropy-decoded and dequantised to recover the modulation vector. This recovered codeword is then input to the modulation network to generate the FiLM parameters that adjust the intermediate layers of the shared base INR network. By combining these modulation parameters with the coordinate grid of antenna and subcarrier indices, the BS evaluates the base network to reconstruct the full CSI matrix. The strategy naturally supports flexible feedback: the UE can choose the number of inner-loop steps and the quantisation level according to its computational and bandwidth constraints, while the BS uses the same fixed model to decode all variants. This design achieves an efficient trade-off between computation and communication and enables extremely compressed yet accurate CSI feedback.

7.5 Experimental Results

This section presents numerical experiments to evaluate the proposed CSI-INR method for the massive MIMO CSI feedback problem. The Outdoor1 Scenario of DeepMIMO datasets [A19] is adopted as the experimental environment, with an operating frequency of 3.5 GHz.

Figure 7-3 The NMSE performance of different schemes over varying feedback dimensions.

Figure 7-3 compares the Normalized Mean-Squared Error (NMSE) performance of CSI-INR with SotA feature-learning-based schemes (TransNet [CGS+22] and DCRNet [TXF+22]) without quantisation and entropy coding operations across different feedback dimensions. The results show that CSI-INR consistently achieves substantially lower NMSE, especially when the feedback dimension is small, demonstrating its superior ability to extract essential channel information under tight bandwidth constraints. The advantage is most pronounced in the low-bit regime, e.g., feedback lengths of 32, where CSI-INR outperforms the baselines by more than 1.6 dB. However, the performance gap narrows as the feedback dimension increases. This is because larger latent vectors allow Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)-based or transformer-based models to perform reasonably well. These findings highlight that treating CSI as a coordinate-based neural function enables more efficient use of limited feedback resources compared with traditional feature-compression networks.

Figure 7-4 The comparisons of different schemes with quantisation and entropy coding operations.

Figure 7-4 compares the rate-distortion performance of CSI-INR when both quantisation and entropy coding are applied (denoted CSI-INR-Q-E) against three strong baselines: DeepCMC

[MYG21], TransNet, and DCRNet. The figure shows that CSI-INR-Q-E achieves dramatically better NMSE performance across all bit rates, preserving reconstruction quality even at extremely low feedback budgets. In fact, for a target NMSE such as -25 dB, CSI-INR-Q-E requires only about one-fifth of the communication overhead needed by existing methods. This superiority comes from the fact that the modulation vectors produced by CSI-INR remain highly expressive yet remarkably quantisable, enabling entropy coding to extract additional efficient compression without accuracy loss. Overall, Figure 7-4 highlights that combining INR-based modulation with quantisation and arithmetic coding delivers a significant leap in CSI compression efficiency, outperforming the best feature-learning-based methods by up to 11.23 dB in NMSE at the same bit rate.

7.6 Conclusions

In conclusion, this work introduced a new paradigm for CSI compression. In goal-oriented communications, CSI feedback is not an end in itself but a means to enable downstream PHY objectives such as beamforming, link adaptation, localization, or sensing. CSI-INR naturally supports this view by encoding CSI into compact, physically meaningful modulation parameters that can be adapted to the current task and operating conditions. This shifts feedback from transmitting full channel tensors to communicating only the information required to achieve the target PHY-level goal. By combining a meta-learned base INR network, FiLM-based modulation, and lightweight inner-loop optimisation, the proposed CSI-INR framework achieved SotA reconstruction accuracy under extremely low feedback budgets. Its modulation vectors were shown to be highly quantisable, and when paired with arithmetic entropy coding, the system delivered substantial rate-distortion gains, reducing feedback overhead by up to a factor of five while maintaining excellent NMSE performance. The approach also offered flexible feedback strategies, allowing users to adapt the number of modulation steps to their computational resources. Overall, the results demonstrated that reconceptualizing CSI as a coordinate-based neural function yields a powerful, physically meaningful, and bandwidth-efficient solution for future massive MIMO systems.

8 Conclusions

In this section, we provide an overall perspective on the contributions of this deliverable, summarising its main technical advancements, emphasizing its links to other project deliverables, and outlining promising directions for future work.

8.1 Technical Advancements

This deliverable advances the 6G-GOALS vision by showing how Model Management (caching, training, and compression) can be systematically embedded across the 6G protocol stack and different application frameworks, rather than being treated as isolated mechanisms. The document outlines five key contributions (A-E) in model management for 6G networks, each tied to specific functions like caching, training, or compression across protocol layers. Below is a summary of each contribution.

Contribution A advances model caching and compression in the SEMDAS framework at MAC/application layers, where a shared encoder ML model resides primarily at the edge server and is distributed to resource-constrained IoT devices for local caching and semantic relevance scoring. Key advancements include characterizing the encoder compactness vs. semantic detection accuracy trade-off via pruning (up to 40-60% overhead reduction), and proposing hierarchical memories for selective caching of context-relevant components alongside lightweight foundation models to preserve semantic space quality under device constraints. This enables context-aware random access, reducing irrelevant transmissions while addressing communication overhead from model sharing.

Contribution B focuses on model caching for real-time multimodal inference at the edge (application layer), caching pre-trained AV foundation models at an MA to fuse asynchronous streams from devices under modality-specific delays. Advancements feature a neuro-inspired TWI wrapper (PaMo/ToMo variants) that optimizes data-flow for temporal coherence, achieving 400-1000 ms latency reductions with <5% accuracy loss vs. state-of-the-art without fixed reference modalities. This caching strategy handles stochastic communication uncertainties, enabling reliable edge inference for AI services like event localization.

Contribution C targets model training and compression in SL for transformer architectures (e.g., ViTs), splitting the model between client (edge/device) and server (cloud) across data/application layers to exchange compressed activations/gradients. The ADC advances batch clustering via attention scores and token sparsification, yielding >50% compression gains without auxiliary networks or accuracy loss, even at low batch sizes. This supports communication-efficient distributed training in bandwidth-limited edge-to-cloud pipelines, preserving performance across datasets like Food-101.

Contribution D addresses model training and compression in Reinforcement Learning for DI-MDPs under delays, applicable to control tasks across network/application layers with models managed at the receiver (edge/cloud) using transmitter data. Advancements include a train-compress-refine-retrain-deploy cycle: belief-space discretization for offline compression (>100x training time reduction), rolling-horizon DP with rollout refinement for online updates, minimising directed information while surpassing full models in cost and fidelity. This enables scalable, adaptive controllers in constrained cyber-physical systems, interpreting distortion as task-fidelity for semantic compression.

Contribution E specializes in model compression (with caching implications) at the PHY layer for massive MIMO CSI feedback, caching a meta-learned base INR network at UE and BS while exchanging short per-user modulation codewords. The CSI-INR scheme with FiLM modulation, uniform quantization, and entropy coding achieves up to 24.6x bit-rate reduction and 11 dB NMSE gains vs. baselines under low budgets (e.g., 32 bits). This provides flexible, task-adaptive CSI representations for 6G links, shifting from tensor transmission to goal-oriented modulation vectors.

In summary, the contributions in D3.3 collectively advance model management in 6G-GOALS by orchestrating caching, training, and compression across PHY, MAC, and application layers, enabling efficient ML deployment from devices to the cloud. From SEMDAS encoder distribution (A) and edge-cached multimodal fusion (B) to split-training compression (C), delay-robust RL policies (D), and INR-based CSI feedback (E), these frameworks achieve key quantitative targets like 24-60% overhead reductions, 400+ ms latency gains, and scalable semantic processing under constraints. Together, they pave the way for AI-native networks that deliver low-latency, energy-efficient, goal-oriented services across diverse use cases from IoT to network management.

8.2 Broader Impact within 6G-GOALS

From a broader perspective on the 6G-GOALS project, this document operationalizes the high-level model management ideas and semantic lifecycle concepts (e.g., Semantic Communication Operations, SemComOps, and semantic management loops from WP2 [GHS+24]) by instantiating them in four concrete frameworks and associated methodologies. It first treats SEMDAS as a SemComOps-style model caching and compression problem, where a shared encoder is distributed to IoT devices and its size-accuracy trade-off is characterized via pruning-based semantic-space degradation curves, with continual/federated learning and hierarchical memories proposed as concrete strategies to maintain a high-quality latent space under device constraints. Real-time multimodal inference is then cast as a temporal model caching of an AV foundation model at an edge multimodal aggregator, wrapped by a neuro-inspired TWI

mechanism (PaMo/ToMo) that explicitly optimises the accuracy–latency trade-off under stochastic, modality-specific delays, aligning with SemComOps goals of goal-oriented, context-aware inference. For training, the deliverable introduces ADC for SL of transformers, combining batch-wise clustering in attention space and token-level sparsification to compress intermediate activations and gradients without auxiliary networks, thereby providing a concrete split-training pipeline that implements “model training + communication-efficient compression” jointly within a SemComOps pipeline. Reinforcement Learning for delayed constrained systems is framed as DI-MDP model management, with an explicit train–compress–refine–retrain–deploy loop based on belief-space discretization, rolling-horizon DP, and rollout, offering a structured methodology for compressed controllers that are refined online, in line with semantic lifecycle management. Finally, CSI-INR gives a PHY-layer instantiation of model compression and caching: a meta-learned implicit neural representation with per-user modulation codewords, uniform quantisation, and arithmetic coding, yielding a concrete CSI feedback protocol where only short, task-adaptive modulation vectors are exchanged while a shared base network is cached at UE and BS, exemplifying SemComOps principles for in-network semantic/ML models.

8.3 Future Directions

Future work will focus on consolidating the mapping of each of the Contributions A-E and the project-level objectives, QTs, KPIs, and use cases, by refining the traceability table introduced in Section 2. On the technical side, promising directions include designing scalable semantic encoders that combine hierarchical memories and lightweight foundation models for SEMDAS, extending the neuro-inspired wrapper to richer multimodal tasks and larger foundation models, and further automating TWI and caching decisions using online learning. For training and control, an important line of work is to generalize ADC and DI-MDP model-management pipelines to broader classes of transformer and RL architectures, exploring tighter accuracy–latency–bandwidth trade-offs and robustness under distribution shifts. In CSI management, future efforts will investigate task-aware CSI-INR variants that jointly optimise feedback for beamforming, sensing, and localization, and will study their behaviour in more realistic 6G scenarios and hardware-constrained deployments. Across these fronts, a key priority is to consolidate the quantified gains of the proposed model-management techniques — evaluated in terms of project QTs such as energy efficiency, timeliness, communication overhead, spectrum efficiency, and scalability — and to feed these insights into later 6G-GOALS deliverables and standardization-relevant guidelines.

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10 Annex

Table 10-1 Quantitative targets set in the 6G-GOALS project

QT	KPI	Improvement Absolute or relative	Current value in 3GPP R17/R18	Target value at the end of the project	Justification
QT1	Energy efficiency	relative	3GPP TR 38.684	50% (at least) reduction measured per accurate task execution.	Semantic communications will drastically reduce the amount of data being generated, communicated and processed
QT2	Timeliness	absolute	3GPP TR	99,999%	Meeting the requirement for latency as well as timely/fresh data arrival as judged by the task accuracy based on the use of predictive AI/ML modules.
QT3	Communication overhead	relative	3GPP R18	25-50%	Semantic communication is capable of suppressing transmission of irrelevant control signalling and data.
QT4	Goal-oriented spectrum efficiency	absolute	3GPP R18	New measure to be defined by 6G- GOALS (WP2)	Ensuring effective share of communication spectrum resources and coexistence of semantic-empowered and legacy communication systems (i.e., data-oriented) systems.
QT5	Scalability	relative	3GPP R18	2x more devices able to connect within the same spectrum	Ensuring that the communication capability can match the increase in intelligence and will not hinder the distributed computing power.